

Harmonisation of life cycle assessment practices in horizon Europe battery technology projects

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ABSTRACT

The transition towards a sustainable and circular battery economy in Europe requires robust and comparable assessments of environmental impacts across the battery value chain. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is widely applied in EU-funded battery research and innovation, yet the methodological diversity across projects limits comparability, benchmarking and policy relevance. This paper, developed within the Battery Heroes sustainability working group, reviews current LCA practices across five Horizon Europe battery projects. The analysis focuses on key methodological elements that influence results, including functional units, system boundaries, end-of-life modelling and allocation, electricity modelling, background data choices, LCIA methods, and impact category coverage. The results show emerging convergence in the key methodological choices. These include the use of capacity-based functional units (1 kWh), reliance on ecoinvent databases, and increasing adoption of the Environmental Footprint (EF3.1) method. However, substantial variability persists in boundary definitions, recycling modelling approaches, electricity assumptions and reporting practices, which can significantly affect interpretation. Based on identified barriers and practitioners' experience, the paper proposes a minimum harmonised reporting set to improve transparency, robustness, and cross-project comparability. These recommendations support alignment with EU regulatory frameworks including EF/Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method and the EU Battery Regulation.

1. Introduction

Europe is accelerating the transition to a sustainable energy system, with battery technologies playing a central role in enabling electrified transport and integrating renewable energy sources. In 2024, Europe accounted for 13% of global battery production capacity (totalling 729 GWh), and energy demand is expected to increase substantially as the uptake of electric vehicles continues (Deloitte, 2025). The European Commission (EC) launched the European Battery Alliance in 2017, bringing together European countries, industry, and the scientific community to establish Europe as a global leader in sustainable battery production (European Commission, 2017). The European Green Deal, adopted in 2019, introduces procedures to transform the EU economy towards climate neutrality by 2050, highlighting the need for consistent,

transparent, and reliable environmental assessments to support this transition (European Commission, 2019). As renewable energy sources become increasingly dominant (25.4% in 2024 and expected to increase to 42.5% in 2030), batteries provide the critical storage capacity needed to manage intermittency and ensure grid stability (EEA, 2025).

Major European research initiatives, including Battery2030+ and the Batteries Europe Technology Roadmap, have outlined ambitious goals for developing next-generation battery technologies that are more efficient, cost-effective and environmentally sustainable throughout their life cycle (Batteries Europe, 2025; Battery 2030+, 2023). For instance, by 2035, NMC lithium-ion cells are targeted to reach 350 Wh/kg specific energy and 10 kWh/kWh_{cell} energy use on the cell level (Batteries Europe, 2025). In terms of environmental impacts, they estimate a range of 12–24 kg CO₂-eq/kWh_{cell} based on cradle-to-gate

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(including material extraction/production and manufacturing processes) climate change impacts reported in the literature (Batteries Europe, 2025). The new strategic plan focuses on reducing reliance on critical foreign raw materials by developing alternatives, including biobased materials, and by increasing circularity (Battery 2030+, 2023). The last Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda by the EC and the Batteries European Partnership (BEPA, 2024) identifies the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework as one of the “six imperatives” to support the competitive battery value chain in Europe. The SSbD framework aims to support the design and development of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials within the research and innovation phase (Aguirre et al., 2025). It integrates circularity and functionality with sustainability considerations throughout the life cycles of chemicals and materials to minimise their environmental footprint. The transition to a circular, environmentally sustainable battery economy is also reinforced by recent regulatory developments, particularly the EU Battery Regulation (European Parliament and Council, 2023), which mandates stringent sustainability and transparency requirements. These include carbon footprint declarations, responsible sourcing of raw materials through due diligence, recycled-content targets, and the implementation of Digital Battery Passports. Together, these instruments reflect a paradigm shift in how battery technologies are expected to contribute to energy security and long-term environmental management (European Commission, 2017).

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a standardised methodology for evaluating environmental impacts across all product life stages (ISO 14040, 2006; ISO 14044, 2006). Within battery innovation projects, LCA is increasingly used to identify hotspots, compare cell chemistries, and inform design choices that reduce environmental burdens. The EC and the Horizon Europe research program explicitly encourage the integration of LCA into research projects as a means to ensure that technological progress aligns with sustainability goals (European Commission, 2022). The EC also promotes the need for efficient, simplified LCA applications aligned with EC Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methods and the SSbD framework to support the implementation of the Batteries Regulation and other EU strategies.

Despite its established methodology, the application of LCA in EU-funded battery projects remains fragmented. Various projects employ different system boundaries, functional units (FU), impact assessment methods, and assumptions regarding datasets, resulting in often incomparable and difficult-to-interpret results in policy or industrial contexts. Moreover, inconsistent data availability further compromises the reliability and replicability of LCA results. These challenges limit LCA's potential to serve as a harmonised benchmarking tool across battery research initiatives and delay the transition towards more sustainable, circular battery value chains.

Against this background, this paper aims to support consistency and comparability of battery LCA results within EU battery research and innovation. Specifically, it (i) provides an overview of LCA practice in battery research, (ii) reviews how LCA is currently implemented in five Horizon Europe battery projects, (iii) identifies key barriers to comparability across projects, and (iv) proposes practical recommendations from an LCA practitioner perspective to improve transparency, robustness, and alignment with emerging EU regulatory frameworks.

The review was conducted through three complementary approaches: (i) structured document analysis of publicly available and internal project deliverables; (ii) a structured comparison template developed within the Battery Heroes Sustainability working group, applied consistently across all five projects to assess the same analytical dimensions (FU, system boundaries, allocation, databases, Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method, impact categories, electricity modelling, sensitivity analysis, and upscaling); and (iii) iterative validation workshops with LCA practitioners from each project team, ensuring consistency and completeness of the information gathered.

1.1. Life cycle assessment in battery research

The EU Battery Regulation adopts integrated environmental assessment approaches, including mandatory carbon footprint declarations, to enhance sustainability throughout battery value chains, from raw material extraction to end-of-life treatment (European Parliament and Council, 2023). This regulation aims to promote environmentally conscious innovation and circular economy principles by requiring harmonised impact assessment frameworks, ensuring that environmental claims about battery products are supportable and consistent across the EU market. The focus on methodological alignment in these policies facilitates improved data sharing, regulatory compliance, and market transparency, reinforcing the EU's leadership in sustainable technology development and circular economy practices.

LCA is an essential tool in technology development, providing a structured way to quantify and compare the environmental impacts of emerging technologies, materials, and processes as they progress from laboratory or pilot scale to potential industrial implementation. When LCA is used in the early stages of technology development, it enables innovators to evaluate how their design and process choices may affect environmental performance. It helps identify data gaps and prioritise areas for improvement. By adjusting the level of detail and project specificity with various stages of scaling up and project maturity, LCA facilitates informed decision-making that incorporates environmental sustainability considerations into research and development. This proactive approach transforms LCA from a retrospective evaluation tool into a guiding framework that influences technology design, scaling strategies, and innovation pathways, all aimed at reducing environmental burdens and achieving more sustainable outcomes (Riondet et al., 2024).

Furthermore, ensuring methodological consistency in LCA is important for advancing environmental research and practice, as harmonised methodologies make comparing, reproducing, and integrating studies significantly easier, leading to more reliable interpretations of environmental performance across diverse systems, products, and contexts. Implementing clear procedures to verify completeness, consistency, and data quality is essential to maintaining transparency and coherence throughout the assessment process. Such alignment facilitates the development of robust datasets and enables meaningful benchmarking across technologies or sectors. Ultimately, establishing a shared methodological foundation promotes effective data exchange, enhances the credibility of LCA outcomes, and strengthens the role in guiding decisions in sustainability, policy-making and industry practices (Cerchione et al., 2025).

In battery-focused LCAs, the goal and scope definition are particularly crucial. They determine the system boundaries (e.g., cradle-to-gate or cradle-to-grave) (ISO 14044, 2006), the FU (often defined as kWh energy delivered over its lifetime, or kWh capacity of a battery pack ($\text{kWh}_{\text{battery}}$), or kg of a battery pack or even driven km) (Carvalho et al., 2021; Quan et al., 2022) and the allocation methods for multi-output processes. The inventory analysis phase involves collecting quantitative data on energy and material inputs, emissions, and waste flows for each stage of the battery value chain. The inventory data are sourced from a combination of primary industrial datasets, laboratory measurements, and secondary databases such as ecoinvent, LCA for Experts, or ELCD (Fan et al., 2023; Quan et al., 2022; Shu et al., 2021). The impact assessment phase then translates inventory flows into environmental impact categories, typically using methods such as the Environmental Footprint (EF), ReCiPe, or CML (Botejara-Antúnez et al., 2024; Gutsch and Leker, 2024; Lai et al., 2022). Commonly evaluated impact categories in battery LCAs include climate change, resource depletion, acidification, and water use.

While comparisons of EU battery LCA guidelines have appeared in recent literature (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023; Eltohamy et al., 2024), Table 1 here serves as a contextual reference frame for the cross-project analysis in Section 3, enabling a direct assessment of how closely

Table 1
Comparison of the guidelines for battery LCA.

Guideline	FU	System boundaries	Use phase	End-of-life modelling	Environmental impact categories
PEFCR (High Specific Energy Rechargeable Batteries for Mobile Applications)	1 kWh of the total energy provided over the service life by the battery	Cradle-to-grave, includes a charge for ICT (information and communication technology)/CPT (cordless power tools) equipment	Energy losses due to the battery and charger efficiency	CFF	All EF impact categories
CFB-EV	1 kWh of the total energy provided over the service life by the battery	Whole life-cycle, excluding the use stage	Excluded	CFF	Climate change (EF3.1)
CFB-IND	1 kWh of the total energy provided over the service life by the battery, measured in kWh for repetitive energy supply (REP) Or Provision of 1 kWmin of backup power capability over the whole service life for on-demand (OND) batteries (backup)	Whole life-cycle, excluding the use stage	Excluded	CFF	Climate change (EF3.1)
DA-EV (Commission Delegated Regulation Supplementing Regulation (EU) 2023/1542)	1 kWh of the total energy provided over the service life by the battery, measured in kWh	Whole life-cycle, excluding the use stage	Excluded	CFF	Climate change (EF3.1)

research practices align – or diverge – from regulatory expectations.

Several EU guidelines on battery LCA differ in their aims, system boundaries, FU, end-of-life (EoL) modelling, and impact assessment methods. The Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCR), the draft delegated act establishing the methodology for the calculation and verification of the carbon footprint of electric vehicle batteries according to the Battery Regulation (DA-EV) (European Commission, 2024), the draft rules for the calculation of the carbon footprint of electric vehicle batteries (CFB-EV) (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023), and the methodology for calculation and verification of the carbon footprint of rechargeable industrial batteries (CFB-IND) (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2025) target different goals; PEFCR is voluntary, while the others require mandatory carbon footprint declarations. PEFCR uses a cradle-to-grave boundary, but DA-EV, CFB-EV, and CFB-IND exclude use-stage impacts. The FU is generally “1 kWh” over the battery's life, except for industrial backup batteries, where FU relates to backup power capacity. Total energy calculations differ among frameworks. Use-stage energy considers only efficiency losses; future battery degradation isn't modelled, but PEFCR notes 60 cycles/year. All use the circular footprint formula (CFF) for end-of-life, and while DA-EV, CFB-EV, and CFB-IND focus on climate change impact, PEFCR covers all impact categories. The PEFCR includes all EF impact categories, with no exclusions.

In scientific literature, there is a large discrepancy between battery LCA studies; recent reviews highlight that most studies rely on a battery capacity-based FU or a mass-based FU (Gillet et al., 2025; Scrucca et al., 2025). Notably, the kWh delivered FU recommended in the PEFCR, DA-EV, CFB-EV and CFB-IND guidelines was applied in 9 studies out of 72 battery LCA studies (Gillet et al., 2025).

In parallel, comparability is further limited by methodological inconsistencies. Climate change is the most frequently assessed impact category, even though LCA aims to avoid burden-shifting by considering multiple environmental impact categories. With respect to LCIA, the European EF method is still less frequently adopted than ReCiPe in battery LCA studies (Gillet et al., 2025; Scrucca et al., 2025), which hampers comparison with studies aligned with European product environmental policy and the draft DA-EV methodological recommendation.

2. Overview of European horizon battery projects

The Battery Heroes working group is a collaborative platform within European battery research that promotes knowledge exchange, methodological alignment, and sustainability innovation across five Horizon EU-funded projects. Comprising research institutions, industrial

partners, and sustainability experts, it fosters cross-project discussions on topics such as LCA and the EU Battery Regulation. By enabling synergies through Horizon Europe, the initiative supports harmonised methodologies and boosts the impact of EU battery research.

GIGAGREEN advances Europe's battery sector by developing scalable processes for generation 3b lithium-ion cells, focusing on sustainability, cost efficiency, and flexibility, while enhancing performance and safety. It aims to accelerate NMP-free wet processing, explore dry processing, and move from laboratory (TRL 3–4) to pilot stages (TRL 5–6), leading to prototype demos. Sustainability is assessed through LCA using ISO 14040/44 standards. The project targets a 25% reduction in energy use and costs in cell manufacturing (GIGAGREEN, n.d.).

BatWoMan focuses on sustainable manufacturing innovations and material efficiency, as well as other water-based processing, 3D electrode structuring, reduced dry room requirements, and improved formation. An AI-based platform and a digital battery dataspace, along with passport support, facilitate these technological improvements. The overall goal of the project was to reduce the production cost and energy consumption by more than 50% (BatWoMan, n.d.).

NoVOC aims to implement an environmentally friendly, non-toxic lithium-ion battery process at pilot scale, covering manufacturing, design, and assembly. It uses aqueous and dry electrode methods to cut costs and environmental impact. The project cycles through understanding automotive needs, sharing with battery makers and R&D teams, developing new components, and recycling end-of-life materials. Innovations are assessed through LCA and economic analysis throughout the project (NoVOC, n.d.).

GIGABAT is focused on strengthening the EU battery cell manufacturing industry and its value chain by engaging key players to develop GEN3b (Li-ion) batteries. This includes developing new, energy-efficient cell manufacturing machinery tailored to Gigafactory needs, and validating it in pilot plants to ensure proper operation in real-world environments. The project also targets the optimisation of Gigafactories via sector coupling, promoting sustainability, improving carbon footprint and energy management, and digitalising the machinery (GIGABAT, n.d.).

BATMACHINE develops new machinery for battery cell production to reduce energy use, improve efficiency, and lower scrap. The project includes automated slurry mixing, innovative slot-die coating and drying machinery, and a calendaring tool for process optimisation. It also integrates intelligent controls and Industry 4.0 via a collaborative, FAIR data space. The project assesses the environmental, social and economic impacts of various machinery, configurations, and factory designs to cut costs and energy consumption (BATMACHINE, n.d.).

To complement the narrative description of each horizon battery project, Table 2 provides a consolidated overview of the projects, including their duration, targeted battery chemistries, and key LCA deliverables.

Collectively, the analysed Horizon Europe projects demonstrate a notable degree of methodological alignment in their sustainability approaches, particularly in the systematic application of LCA throughout the technology development stages. All projects incorporate LCA as a core evaluation tool, with deliverables spanning from early screening assessments to comprehensive full-scale LCA studies. This alignment is evident in shared commitment to addressing key environmental indicators – including energy consumption reduction and carbon footprint optimisation – and in the adoption of standardised frameworks such as ISO 14040/44.

While methodological variations naturally arise from differences in battery chemistries and technological objectives, the projects show convergence on fundamental assessment principles. The progression from screening LCA at the early stage to full LCA/LCSA at pilot and prototype scales reflects a coordinated approach to integrating sustainability considerations throughout the innovation cycle as suggested by the SSbD framework. This emerging harmonisation across EU-funded battery initiatives is particularly valuable in light of the regulatory requirements introduced by the EU Battery Regulation. It demonstrates the effectiveness of collaborative platforms in fostering methodological consistency and the exchange of best practices.

3. Current practices in battery LCA: A review of methodological approaches across five horizon Europe battery projects

The European Union's Horizon Europe program has invested significantly in research on sustainable energy storage technologies, aiming to innovate and incorporate environmental assessments from the outset. This aligns with the European Green Deal and battery regulations. This section reviews how LCA is applied in selected Horizon Europe battery projects to evaluate methodological consistency and identify sources of variability affecting result comparability.

This analysis reviews five Horizon Europe projects (GIGAGREEN, BatWoMan, NoVOC, GIGABAT, and BATMACHINE) to assess key LCA elements: (i) FU and reference flow, (ii) system boundaries and life cycle stages (including use phase), (iii) allocation and end-of-life models, (iv) background datasets and electricity assumptions, (v) software tools, and (vi) impact assessment methods and categories. Mapping and comparing these elements offer an overview of current LCA practices in EU-funded battery R&I, highlighting converging approaches and methodological gaps to inform future harmonisation aligned with the EU Battery Regulation and EF framework.

3.1. Cross-project overview of LCA practices

Across the five projects, LCA is applied as a staged process (from screening to full LCA/LCSA), typically supported by internal workshops

to inform eco-design decisions.

The GIGAGREEN project aims to develop scalable electrode and cell manufacturing to reduce environmental impact and energy use, design cells for reuse and disassembly, and improve cost and safety. The LCA study starts by defining baseline conditions to identify environmental hotspots and areas for improvement. Based on literature and partner input, NMC 811 cathode and graphite anode are the baseline chemistry. A literature review established that 1 kWh of battery capacity is the FU, with cradle-to-gate system boundaries, using the ReCiPe 2016 v1.1 method and Ecoinvent v3.9.1 database for impact assessment. The inventory data were adapted from Italy to China's electricity mix, reflecting China's production focus. These practices will inform the final environmental analysis.

The BatWoMan project aimed to follow Battery regulation throughout the life cycle, but was unable to implement with the CFF for end-of-life due to missing guidance, instead using normal system expansion with credits for recovered materials. Battery capacity in kWh was the primary unit, with delivery kWh and per-vehicle km also calculated. A multiplier converted per-kWh capacity to delivered kWh over the battery's life. Climate impact, resource depletion (ultimate reserves), acidification, and photochemical ozone formation were assessed using EF 3.1, with a focus on climate impact. The European electricity mix served as the base case, with variations using Swedish and Chinese mixes. Cell weight in packs and formation was also explored. Scaling involved industrial cell formats, but production remained at pilot scale. The three-year LCA began with literature-based early-stage assessments, leading to workshops on sustainable design and scope. The early-stage LCA used data from a study by von Drachenfels et al., 2023 modelling NMC622 impacts, which became the baseline for the full LCA.

In NoVOC, an early-stage LCA focused on the dry and wet processing of NMC811 cells, including the entire battery pack and the full life cycle, except the use phase. Data were mainly from literature, re-modelled, and adapted for the project's cells. An idea-generation workshop in month 12 presented early LCA results and brainstormed environmental improvements. A goal-and-scope workshop a year before the project end sets LCA boundaries, following the Battery Regulation methodology for carbon footprint, though delayed guidelines may limit this. Life Cycle Costing is planned for the end.

GIGABAT adopted a similar LCA approach to BatWoMan and NoVOC, including early-stage LCAs, idea generation, and goal- and scoping-workshops. The early-stage LCA focused on large-scale production of NMC811 and LFP cells, covering the entire battery pack and lifecycle, excluding the use phase. A use-phase scenario was developed to avoid total exclusion, and a literature review on recycling impacts was conducted. Consideration of the Battery Regulation methodology for carbon footprint declarations is planned but delayed. The project also includes an absolute environmental sustainability assessment to be integrated into the final LCA, with targets derived from frameworks such as the planetary boundaries and carbon budgets (Ali et al., 2025).

To align with the BATMACHINE project's focus on developing new battery cell manufacturing machinery, a cradle-to-gate LCA is conducted

Table 2
Summary of horizon battery projects.

Projects	Duration	Primary Objective	TRL Range	Chemistries	Key Innovation	LCA deliverables
BatWoMan	2022–2025	Sustainable manufacturing & material efficiency	TRL 4–6	NMC622	Water-based processing, 3D electrode structuring	Screening LCA, full LCA
NoVOC	2023–2026	Non-toxic LiB process at pilot scale	TRL 4–6	NMC811	Aqueous and dry electrode methods	Screening LCA, full LCA
GIGABAT	2023–2026	Strengthen EU battery cell manufacturing	TRL 5–6	NMC811 and LFP	Energy-efficient gigafactory machinery	Screening LCA, full LCA
GIGAGREEN	2022–2026	Scalable Gen3b cell manufacturing	TRL 3–5	LNMO	LNMO chemistry, NMP-free processing	Preliminary Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) lab scale, full LCSA upscaled
BATMACHINE	2023–2026	New machinery for battery cell production	TRL 4–6	NMC811, LFP, NMC622	Automated coating, calendaring, and Industry 4.0	LCSA of SoA LIB production, LCSA of different supply chains

for two benchmark cells using primary data (the report is available here: D5.1 - Sustainability assessment of state-of-the-art lithium-ion cell production). The first cell is an LFP-100 Ah cell, and the second is an NMC622-Gr cell. The system boundaries are taken from (Andreas Bassi et al., 2023), but to meet the project objective, the FU is not aligned with the draft CF rules; rather, it is 1 kWh of storage capacity. The background database is Ecoinvent 3.9.1, and the LCIA method is EF 3.1. Not only environmental but also social LCA is included, using the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB). While social LCA is within scope for both BATMACHINE and GIGAGREEN's LCSA framework, harmonising social assessment practices across EU battery projects is beyond the scope of the present paper, which focuses specifically on environmental LCA, and is identified as a priority for future work.

Table 3 provides an overview of the methodological LCA practices adopted across the selected Horizon Europe projects, highlighting differences and similarities in FU, system boundaries, allocation method and environmental impact categories.

Table 3 highlights current methodological choices in Horizon Europe battery projects. LCA is increasingly central, used iteratively from screening to full LCAs. Methodological convergence includes using 1 kWh as a reference and ecoinvent as the main database. This alignment supports EU sustainability policies and enhances comparability across projects. Table 3 also shows significant variability in modelling choices that affect results, including system boundaries, multi-functionality handling, electricity supply modelling, LCIA methods, and impact categories. EF3.1 is common but not universal, with climate change being the most assessed category.

Overall, these inconsistencies reduce comparability, complicate

benchmarking, and limit the use of LCA outputs as harmonised evidence for technology prioritisation and policy-aligned reporting. The practical significance of these methodological differences can be illustrated with a concrete example from the reviewed projects. For the NMC622 battery system developed in the BatWoMan project, cradle-to-gate climate change impacts ranged from 72 to 90 kg CO₂eq/kWh of battery capacity, depending on assumptions about the electricity mix used for cell manufacturing and graphite production. This 20% variation — driven exclusively by methodological choices rather than differences in battery technology — demonstrates that harmonising key modelling assumptions is essential for meaningful cross-project comparisons. Based on the methodological overview presented in Table 3, the main methodological barriers commonly encountered across the analysed projects are discussed below.

3.1.1. Barriers in LCA across projects

Working with sustainability assessments presents challenges and barriers, both methodological and technical. This also applies to battery-related assessments, where some barriers are common to most assessments, and others are specific to the process/product/service being assessed. One of the objectives of the Battery Heroes Sustainability working group has been to identify existing barriers across various projects and to share experiences, exploring the possibility of jointly addressing them.

The following main barriers were identified within the working group:

- i) Lack of a single guidance document for battery LCAs;

Table 3

Methodological overview of LCA practices adopted so far across selected Horizon Europe projects. Note that the final studies for several projects are still in progress (✓ = aligned, ~ = partial alignment, × = not aligned).

Practice/Project	GIGAGREEN	BatWoMan	NoVOC	GIGABAT	BATMACHINE
Overall alignment	~	✓	✓	✓	✓
Alignment with Battery Regulation	Partial – uses ReCiPe instead of EF; cradle-to-gate only	Partial – EF3.1 adopted; CFF not yet implemented	Partial – EF3.1 planned; CFF pending guidelines	Partial – EF3.1 adopted; CFF planned	Partial – EF3.1 adopted; cradle-to-gate only
FU(s)	1 kWh battery capacity	1 kWh battery capacity (1 kWh delivered energy; Vehicle kilometre)	1 kWh battery capacity, 1 kWh delivered energy	1 kWh battery capacity, 1 kWh delivered energy	1 kWh battery capacity
System boundaries	Cradle-to-gate	Cradle-to-grave, use phase excluded	Cradle-to-grave scenario for the use phase	Cradle-to-grave scenario for the use phase	Cradle-to-gate
Allocation method	Cut-off	Cut-off, system expansion for recycling credits	Cut-off and/or CFF	Cut-off and/or CFF	Cut-off
Software and databases	SimaPro and Ecoinvent 3.9.1	SimaPro and Ecoinvent 3.9.1	SimaPro and Ecoinvent 3.11	SimaPro, Brightway and Ecoinvent 3.11	Brightway and Ecoinvent 3.9.1
Impact Assessment Method	ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	Environmental Footprint 3.1	Environmental Footprint 3.1	Environmental Footprint 3.1 & Absolute Environmental Sustainability Assessment	Environmental Footprint 3.1
Environmental impact categories	ReCiPe midpoint indicators	Climate, resource depletion, acidification, photochemical oxidation, cumulative energy demand	EF3.1 midpoint indicators and CED	EF3.1 midpoint indicators and CED	EF3.1 midpoint indicators
Electricity mix (es)	Chinese mix as baseline for production. European mix for production processes. Specific mix for raw materials	Specific mix for raw materials. European mix as base case for production processes. Swedish mix in sensitivity analysis.	Location-based, European average mix as baseline	Location-based, European average mix as baseline	Location-based + hourly mix
Sensitivity analysis	For local, at least the electricity mix	One at a time variations of electricity, % of cells in pack, electricity for graphite, formation protocol, and dry room scenarios.	Local (one at a time) sensitivity analysis, at least for the electricity mix.	Local (one-at-a-time) and global sensitivity analysis. For local, at least the electricity mix.	One at a time: Supply sources, electricity mix
Production scale for LCA model	Industrial scale based on lab experimental data	Industrial scale based on pilot line experiments	Industrial scale based on lab/pilot scale data	Giga (industrial) scale, based on lab/pilot scale data (Degen et al., 2025) and/or (Chordia et al., 2021) for giga-scale and (Ali et al., 2025) for absolute environmental sustainability targets	Industrial scale (some upscaled from pilot scale) Industrial data from the project partner, already been delivered: D5.1 - Sustainability assessment of state-of-the-art lithium-ion cell production
Benchmark study	(Carvalho et al., 2021)	(von Drachenfels et al., 2023)	(Degen et al., 2025) and (Chordia et al., 2021)		

- ii) Lack of primary data;
- iii) Discrepancy in background data;
- iv) End-of-life modelling;
- v) Electricity modelling;
- vi) Lack of up-scaling approaches.

Lack of a single guidance document for battery LCAs.

As discussed, there is currently no single guidance for conducting battery LCA studies, leaving practitioners with several methodological choices. This limits comparability and hampers decision-making. Nonetheless, harmonisation is underway at regulatory and industrial levels. For example, mandatory carbon footprint declarations under the Battery Regulation aim to enable comparison and prevent high-carbon footprint batteries from being sold in the EU. However, detailed guidelines, currently delayed in draft form, are needed (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023).

The applicability of the Delegated Act methodology to research contexts poses further challenges. Research projects often operate with scopes and objectives that differ significantly from those of commercial battery production, raising questions about whether the prescribed methodology adequately meets the needs of both regulatory compliance and research innovation. This gap between regulatory frameworks and research requirements may require additional guidance tailored to pre-commercial technology development.

Although the Battery Regulation will provide detailed guidance, it is not straightforward to determine whether the delegated act methodology may apply to research projects with different scopes. The not-yet-finalised PEFCR for batteries provides a broader environmental performance framework beyond carbon footprint (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023). The TranSensus LCA project's guidelines, focused on vehicles, also aid harmonisation (Eltohamy et al., 2024). Despite these efforts, the variety and overlap of initiatives highlight the lack of a single, comprehensive guidance document for battery LCA applications.

3.1.2. Lack of primary data

Data quality impacts LCA reliability, but primary data collection remains a challenge due to confidentiality and unavailability. Confidentiality concerns, especially with proprietary processes or new materials, can limit data sharing, even within limited groups. Data may be unavailable because companies lack measurements or supplier data, leading practitioners to rely on less specific, generic database information.

The consequence of these data limitations is that researchers rely on generic inventories that poorly represent the specific characteristics of emerging battery technologies. These datasets reflect average or mature systems and may miss unique material needs, energy use, and waste patterns of innovative processes. This mismatch introduces uncertainty into assessments, hindering accurate evaluation of environmental impacts. Data quality issues hinder both practical analysis and the credibility of LCA results in guiding battery tech development.

3.1.3. Discrepancy in background data

The background database is crucial in assessing battery impacts, as supply routes of materials heavily influence outcomes. Recent studies reveal that the impact of climate change on battery active materials, especially graphite—used in anodes—has been underestimated. Variability in synthetic graphite's carbon footprint ranges from 13.8 kg CO₂eq/kg (Surovtseva et al., 2022) to 42.2 kg CO₂eq/kg (Carrère et al., 2024), and natural graphite from 5.3 kg CO₂eq/kg (Gao et al., 2018) to 9.6 kg CO₂eq/kg (Engels et al., 2022). Updated datasets, such as ecoinvent, show that the impacts of synthetic graphite was underestimated in previous versions, showing an increase of almost ninefold over four years (Table 4). It should be noted that this increase is not solely attributable to the change in IPCC characterisation method (from IPCC 2013 to IPCC 2021 GWP100 between v3.8 and v3.9.1), but primarily reflects updated underlying production data for Chinese

Table 4

Impact on climate change of producing graphite in different ecoinvent versions. Method: IPCC 2013 GWP100 for ecoinvent 3.8 and IPCC 2021 GWP100 for all other versions. All values refer to the cut-off system model.

Ecoinvent version (year)	Impact of synthetic graphite (kg CO ₂ eq/kg)	Impact of natural graphite (kg CO ₂ eq/kg)
3.12 cut-off (2025)	47.8 (CN)	9.24 (CN)
3.11 cut-off (2024)	47.3 (CN)	8.92 (CN)
3.10.1 cut-off (2024)	7.41 (CN)	–
3.9.1 cut-off (2022)	5.38 (CN)	1.96 (CN)
3.8 cut-off (2021)	5.44 (CN)	2.10 (CN)

synthetic graphite, including revised electricity consumption for the graphitisation process and expanded system boundaries based on Carrère et al. (2024) for synthetic graphite and on Engels et al. (2022) for natural graphite. It's vital to specify the background database, system models, and version used.

All values refer to the cut-off system model; analogous variations are seen under APOS and consequential models, but are not reported here, as all reviewed projects adopt the cut-off approach. The increase between v3.8 and 3.12 primarily reflects updated production data for Chinese synthetic graphite (revised electricity consumption for the graphitisation process and expanded system boundaries), not solely the change in IPCC characterisation method.

3.1.4. End-of-life modelling

The challenge in end-of-life modelling is common to most LCA studies (Ekvall et al., 2023), involving accounting for material recovery, recycling, and environmental credits, which significantly affect life-cycle results, especially in battery LCAs. There is no consensus on the method (Nordelöf et al., 2019), as practitioners adapt approaches based on study scope, data, and preferences, leading to methodological heterogeneity that hampers comparability. The draft regulations specify the circular footprint formula, which is complex and open to interpretation (Rydberg et al., 2023). One reason is that it contains several factors that should be populated, e.g., a factor allocating burdens and credits between life cycles (A factor), quality-related factors (Q factors), and factors related to recycled content (R factors), which are challenging to interpret and implement correctly. For the main battery materials, default values are available in the draft delegated act (European Commission, 2024), including an A factor of 0.2 for most materials, such as cobalt, nickel, and lithium; recycled content values of 0 for all materials; and quality factors of either 1 or 0.8. As shown in Table 3, Battery Heroes practitioners generally use the cut-off methodology for recycling modelling.

3.1.5. Electricity modelling

Modelling electricity consumption in battery production is a critical methodological decision with substantial implications for life cycle impact results, particularly for the carbon footprint indicator, where electricity can be a dominant contributor. There are different approaches for modelling electricity use, such as market- and location-based approaches. In the draft delegated act for the Battery Regulation, a location-based approach should be adopted, rather than relying on contractual instruments to account for these locations. This is, for example, not in line with the general PEF recommendations, which prescribe supplier-specific data, as highlighted by (Ekvall et al., 2023).

3.1.6. Lack of up-scaling approaches

The assessment of emerging battery technologies poses a unique methodological challenge due to the maturity gap between research-scale development and industrial-scale production. In many research projects, the TRL is relatively low, and for battery production projects, development often occurs on a lab- or pilot-scale. An environmental

assessment, for example, is often limited to small-scale production and is thus less interesting and relevant for conclusions, since the processes are, in most cases, not optimised.

Laboratory and pilot-scale battery production often differ from industrial operations, showing higher scrap rates from process learning and equipment limits. Material losses during handling and processing exceed those of continuous industrial operations. Upscaling methodologies aim to predict environmental performance based on current development, considering process improvements and economies of scale, but the lack of standard methods creates uncertainty. This makes upscaling a barrier and complicates fair comparisons between studies.

The barriers reveal the complexity and changing nature of battery sustainability assessments. While progress occurs through regulatory harmonisation, industry guidelines, and research, significant methodological gaps remain, especially in data, end-of-life modelling, electricity accounting, and the upscaling of emerging technologies. Solving these issues requires aligning regulations, industry practices, and research, with transparent data sharing and consistent methods. Strengthening these areas improves the reliability and comparability of battery LCAs, facilitating better decision-making and supporting sustainable, circular battery technologies.

4. Enabling consistency and comparability in horizon battery LCA studies

This chapter offers practical guidance based on cross-project observations from Section 3 to improve the consistency and comparability of LCA results across Horizon Europe battery projects. It covers key modelling choices that impact outcomes: FU, system boundaries, allocation, end-of-life modelling, LCIA method, impact categories, databases, inventory transparency, electricity modelling, sensitivity analysis, upscaling, and benchmark studies. The goal is not to enforce a single framework but to establish a minimum set of reporting and modelling practices for transparent interpretation and alignment across studies, especially at low TRLs.

4.1. FU definition

Addressing the lack of a single guidance document for battery LCAs, the following recommendation aims to harmonise FU choices across projects while maintaining feasibility at different research stages. Across the reviewed horizon battery projects, 1 kWh of battery capacity is the most frequently adopted FU, reflecting its practicality in early-stage research and its widespread use in the literature. At TRL 3–4, a capacity-based FU is typically the only feasible option given limited performance data; at TRL 5–6, additional reporting of a delivered-energy-based FU with clearly documented assumptions becomes increasingly feasible and is recommended. This choice facilitates comparison between different battery chemistries and manufacturing concepts, particularly when the focus is on materials, energy use, and process efficiency at the cell or pack level. However, this FU does not fully capture performance-related aspects such as cycle life, efficiency losses, or real energy delivery, which become increasingly relevant when comparing technologies with different durability or application profiles.

Regulatory initiatives, such as the draft delegated act on the calculation of EV battery carbon footprint and the PEFCE for batteries, prescribe 1 kWh of delivered energy over the battery's service life as the FU. While this approach improves comparability between batteries placed on the market, its applicability to research projects is limited by data availability and uncertainty. At low TRLs, reliable assumptions about lifetime, depth of discharge, degradation behaviour, and real-world use conditions are often unavailable, making robustly implemented delivered-energy-based FUs difficult to implement.

When reporting results per 1 kWh of battery capacity, the specific capacity measure must be clearly stated. Nameplate capacity, usable

capacity, and beginning-of-life capacity can differ depending on chemistry and cell design. Beginning-of-life nominal capacity is recommended as the default reference measure, as it is the most commonly available and reproducible measure at the research scale.

To balance comparability and feasibility, a dual-functional-unit approach is recommended whenever possible. The primary FU should remain 1 kWh of battery capacity, enabling transparent assessment of material and process innovations. In parallel, a secondary FU based on the delivered energy (kWh delivered over lifetime) may be reported when sufficient performance data or well-justified scenarios are available. When conversion factors are applied – such as those used in BatWoMan, NoVOC, and GIGABAT to translate capacity to delivered energy – the underlying assumptions (cycle life, depth of discharge, efficiency) must be clearly documented. This dual approach maintains research flexibility while building towards regulatory alignment as technologies mature.

4.2. System boundaries modelling

Inconsistent system boundary definitions were identified as a key source of variability across projects. The following recommendations provide guidance on boundary choices that balance comparability with the practical constraints of pre-commercial research. System boundary definition is another key source of variability across battery LCA studies. In the reviewed projects, boundaries range from cradle-to-gate to cradle-to-grave, with the use phase frequently excluded due to uncertainty or misalignment with project scope. Cradle-to-gate boundaries are particularly common in projects focusing on materials development or manufacturing process optimisation, where downstream life cycle stages are either identical across compared options or outside the project's control.

While cradle-to-gate studies are often justified in a research context, their limitations must be clearly acknowledged. Excluding the use and end-of-life phases can mask trade-offs, especially when innovations affect battery lifetime, efficiency, or recyclability. Conversely, full cradle-to-grave modelling introduces additional uncertainty, particularly for emerging technologies, and may rely heavily on assumptions rather than measured data.

The Battery Regulation setting limits for the entire life cycle, excluding the use stage, creates a middle ground that several reviewed projects have adopted or are moving towards. This approach recognises that use-phase impacts depend primarily on end-user electricity sources rather than on battery characteristics, while maintaining accountability for manufacturing and end-of-life impacts. However, complete exclusion of use phase modelling may obscure the relative importance of production versus operational impacts, particularly for technologies with different efficiency profiles.

At TRL 3–4, cradle-to-gate boundaries covering manufacturing processes are typically the most feasible and appropriate scope, relying on literature-based inventories. At TRL 5–6, cradle-to-grave modelling with use-phase scenarios, primary data from pilot lines becomes increasingly viable and is recommended where data allow.

To enhance comparability, it is recommended that the research clearly justify system boundary choices in relation to objectives and TRL and explicitly state which life cycle stages are included or excluded. As a minimum, cradle-to-gate boundaries covering raw material extraction, active material production, cell manufacturing, and pack assembly should be consistently defined and documented. When downstream stages are excluded, scenario-based modelling of the use phase and end-of-life may be included as supplementary analyses to illustrate potential implications without overstating certainty. This staged approach – evident in GIGABAT's development of use phase scenarios alongside the core assessment – provides valuable context while maintaining comparability within defined boundaries.

4.3. End-of-life modelling and allocation approaches

End-of-life modelling was identified as one of the most complex and contested methodological choices across the reviewed projects. The following recommendations aim to reduce heterogeneity in allocation and recycling credit approaches. The commonly used allocation methods for end-of-life modelling within the considered projects are cut-off and CFF. The implementation of the CFF depends on the finalisation of the delegated act, providing guidance on estimating the environmental impacts of the batteries in line with the requirements of Article 7 and Annex II of the Batteries Regulation (Andreas Bassi et al., 2025; European Commission, 2020). In addition to guidance from the EC's Joint Research Centre, literature has also provided guidance towards end-of-life modelling, wherein it is suggested to maintain consistency when implementing cut-off and avoiding burden approaches (Husmann et al., 2023; Nordelöf et al., 2019). It is recommended not to provide credits during end-of-life modelling for recovered materials when using cut-off background databases to avoid double-counting the benefits of recycling (Husmann et al., 2023; Nordelöf et al., 2019). Furthermore, in the case of handling multi-functionality processes, it is recommended to apply allocation of impacts depending on the price differences between the materials recovered, as recommended and implemented by (Ali et al., 2025).

4.4. LCIA method selection and impact category coverage

The diversity of LCIA methods observed across projects, and frequent focus on climate change alone, motivate the following recommendation towards a more consistent and comprehensive impact assessment practice. Convergence on the EF 3.1 method was observed across the selected Horizon Europe projects, indicating increasing alignment with the methodological requirements of the draft delegated act, the draft carbon footprint rules (CFB-EV, CFB-IND), the PEFCR for batteries, and the 2025 Revised SSbD framework developed by the JRC. This indicates shared practices based on emerging regulatory expectations under the EU Battery Regulation. The only major divergence came from GIGA-GREEN, which applied ReCiPe 2016 v1.1. As noted previously, ReCiPe remains common in the global literature but is less prevalent in European studies and is not aligned with EF-based regulatory methods, creating challenges for comparison. This fact reflects the legacy influence of earlier battery LCA studies rather than regulatory compliance. The adoption of EF 3.1 as the default LCIA method for EU studies would ensure comparability and regulatory compatibility, whilst ReCiPe could be considered for secondary assessment or continuity with previous studies, not as the primary method.

Regarding the environmental impact categories, alignment in their selection is growing but is not yet complete. In line with the draft PEFCR for batteries, four of the five projects implemented EF 3.1 midpoint indicators, and three included all 16 impact categories required in PEF studies. This contrasts with the Carbon Footprint of Batteries (CFB EV, CFB IND), which is currently restricted to climate change. The broader selection of EF impact categories reflects increasing awareness of comprehensive environmental profiling, recognising that climate change alone does not capture full environmental trade-offs, and that multi-category impact assessment in LCA prevents burden shifting. The EF3.1 midpoint indicators were complemented by cumulative energy demand (CED) in NoVOC and GIGABAT. CED is an LCI indicator that quantifies total primary energy demand across six energy types, both renewable and non-renewable. It could be useful as an optional supporting indicator to enrich EF midpoint results, especially in energy-intensive systems. However, calculating all EF 3.1 midpoint indicators as the default set is recommended to standardise the selection of impact categories, in line with the PEFCR guidelines, even if the assessment focuses on selected key indicators. Explicit statements when the focus is on specific indicators could also be pertinent to maintaining transparency.

4.5. Data sources, databases and inventory transparency

The barriers related to lack of primary data and discrepancies in background datasets directly motivate the following recommendations on data selection, documentation, and transparency. All the projects used the same version of the Ecoinvent database, enabling comparison. However, projects that start at different times may use different versions. As highlighted in section 3.1.1, the environmental impacts of battery raw materials in commercial databases are evolving as data quality improves. Material impacts are of high importance in battery LCAs, notably the supply sources of active materials such as nickel sulfate, graphite, cobalt sulfate, lithium components, aluminium, or copper. Those can significantly affect the cradle-to-gate carbon footprint of batteries (Kallitsis et al., 2024), as well as other impact categories such as acidification, toxicity, and particulate matter, by a factor of 4 (Lavigne Philippot et al., 2025). The large variability in the impacts of different supply routes for the same material requires careful selection and documentation of material inventories. The use of average market datasets for raw materials is questionable for representing the impact of batteries. The authors cannot recommend a specific commercial database, but a clear statement of the version used is necessary to ensure comparability. The inventory should be findable, accessible, interoperable and allow the reuse, following the FAIR principles (Ghose, 2024). A human-readable version of the inventory should be provided, as well as a version compatible with at least one current LCA software.

Electricity modelling assumptions.

Given that electricity modelling was identified as a dominant source of variability in carbon footprint results, the following recommendations address the choice of electricity mix and its documentation. Modelling electricity consumption in battery production has substantial implications for life-cycle impact results. There are different approaches for modelling electricity use, such as market- and location-based approaches (where “market-based” implies contractual arrangements specifying a particular electricity mix, which could be the residual mix or a dedicated green mix; “location-based” implies use of the average grid mix for the relevant region). Among the reviewed projects, a location-based approach with a European-average mix was found to be the dominant choice for electricity consumption during production. Some projects will also handle upstream production of raw materials, using other location-based mixes adapted to material sourcing, to increase the representativeness of the LCA.

In the draft delegated act for the Battery Regulation, a location-based approach is prescribed, i.e., the average mix for the region in question should be used. The general PEF recommendations, on the other hand, prescribe a market approach where either supplier-specific data or the residual mix in the region in question is used, as highlighted by (Ekvall et al., 2023).

Research is not production and supplier-specific data (backed by contractual arrangements) is rarely available, thus a location-based approach, i.e., using averages for what is considered likely to be, for example, the location of a future battery production site, is often the choice. In BatWoMan, for example, the European average mix was used as the base case for the production site, and the Swedish mix was used in the sensitivity analysis. For graphite production, both European (base case), Swedish and Chinese electricity were used in the sensitivity analysis. For raw materials, background datasets representing average global production (using the average global electricity mix) were generally chosen.

4.6. Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis

Sensitivity and/or uncertainty analyses are important parts of many LCA studies, which were also seen among the reviewed projects. All projects aim to perform local sensitivity analysis, at least on the electricity mix. Apart from that, several other parameters related to sourcing, pack design, formation protocol, and the dry room are mentioned.

The projects are aligned on that sensitivity analysis should be included and preferably be done by varying significant parameters (one-at-a-time) from a defined base case, and evaluating the results compared to the base case. Significant parameters could be identified in a Sankey diagram, highlighted in earlier studies or related to specific research questions. The electricity mix is always significant in battery studies, as highlighted above, both in cell production and in raw material production (and in the use-phase), motivating its investigation.

Global sensitivity analysis using the Sobol index decomposition has also been considered in the GIGABAT project, wherein (Ali et al., 2025) demonstrate the use of parametric LCA modelling to evaluate combined and interactive effects of multiple uncertain parameters, capturing non-additive interactions that cannot be identified by local sensitivity analysis. Building parametric LCA models also enables performing uncertainty analysis, providing a range of impact values that offer greater value and confidence in interpreting results than deterministic values. Furthermore, simplified LCA impact models as distinct mathematical equations specific to impact categories are provided to be used for LCA purposes without needing to have access to specific LCA software (Ali et al., 2025).

4.7. Upscaling approaches and production scale representativeness

The lack of standardised upscaling approaches was identified as a significant barrier to fair comparison between projects at different TRL levels. The following recommendations aim to improve transparency and consistency in how research-scale data are extrapolated to industrial scenarios. As mentioned above, research is not production, and physical experiments and tests are often conducted on a much smaller scale than during production. Yet, to facilitate comparisons between studies, all projects seem aligned on the idea that final results should aim to represent a future industrial production scale. How the upscaling from lab or pilot scale at lower TRLs is done in the projects was, however, not specified, most likely since there is no clear strategy or method for this, as pointed out in section 3.1.1. At TRL 3–4, upscaling typically relies on literature benchmarks and theoretical process models; at TRL 5–6, primary data from pilot lines becomes available and should be integrated to improve representativeness. This is an area that could benefit from further development of best practices, enhancing comparability while reducing complexity for practitioners. Some guidelines for upscaling are given in the SSbD framework (European Commission et al., 2024), but the applicability to battery production is still not straightforward. More recently, the 2025 SSbD revised framework (Aguirre et al., 2025) (together with the 2026 Commission Recommendation (European Commission, 2026)) provides better guidance on upscaling for decision-support, but not as a predictive model. It uses a tiered and iterative assessment logic explicitly linked to innovation maturity, offering conceptual boundaries to ensure that scale-up claims are credible, transparent, and progressively substantiated. This approach was not considered in the previous version of the SSbD framework. However, it still lacks engineering upscaling equations or predictive industrial parameters. Literature on prospective LCA can serve as a basis for improving the representativeness of LCA results at the production scale, though. (van der Giesen et al., 2020) recommended some upscaling frameworks from engineering and testing multiple pathways rather than a single industrial scenario. The study by (Sacchi et al., 2022) proposed the “premise” tool to enable modifying multiple industrial sectors simultaneously (power, fuels, metals, transport), which is crucial for batteries as a material and energy-intensive across many sectors. Other authors presented a superstructure approach that allows the coexistence of foreground alternatives (lab and pilot scale, early and optimised industrial) while addressing temporal consistency issues through the operationalisation of the “premises” tool (Steubing and Sacchi, 2024).

4.8. Benchmarking practices and reference studies

A benchmark is something to compare with and learn from at many different levels. If a screening or early-stage LCA is conducted in a research project, a benchmark study could provide the data that are often missing at an early stage. The projects seem to use different benchmark studies, which may reflect their different scopes and focuses. In BatWoMan, for example, an LCA study of an NMC622 cell carried out by (von Drachenfels et al., 2023) was found to be a useful source of data for the screening LCA as well as a benchmark for the full LCA, since it focused on the same chemistry and on the manufacturing stage, i.e., just like BatWoMan. In BATMACHINE, an internal benchmark was set by collecting data from an industrial partner, to set current values, before the implementation of the innovative machineries. If the benchmark study is only used to evaluate goals and ambitions, it might be less important to harmonise the choice of study across projects. However, the comparability between projects might be increased by having a common benchmark, which would require a study relevant for all projects.

Within the project GIGABAT, absolute sustainability targets are also derived to facilitate comparison based on science-based frameworks, such as the planetary boundaries and remaining carbon budgets, in addition to relative comparisons of impacts among other LCA studies (Ali et al., 2024, 2025). Upon deriving specific target values, the impacts are compared using an environmental sustainability ratio (i.e., impacts divided by targets) and a probability-based assessment of the likelihood of meeting the derived targets (Ali et al., 2024, 2025).

4.9. Summary of key recommendations

These recommendations highlight that improved comparability across EU battery LCA studies is achievable without restricting research flexibility. A consistent minimum reporting set—focusing on transparent FUs, system boundaries, end-of-life, allocation choices, and prioritising EF3.1 with impact categories—would cut methodological variability. Also, harmonised electricity modelling, sensitivity analysis, and upscaling practices are crucial to prevent hidden differences and boost confidence in comparisons.

Beyond modelling choices, comparability depends on data transparency and traceability. Clear documentation of database versions, system models, FAIR inventories, and benchmarking choices improves reproducibility and cross-project learning. These are crucial as Horizon Europe projects aim to inform EU Battery Regulation reporting. Table 5 summarises the minimum harmonised reporting and modelling requirements for comparability.

Overall, Table 5 synthesises the main methodological recommendations emerging from this review into a minimum harmonised set that can be applied across EU battery R&I projects. By defining consistent reporting practices for FUs, system boundaries, EoL modelling, electricity assumptions, data transparency and robustness checks, the proposed framework directly addresses the main sources of variability identified across projects. This improves the interpretability and comparability of LCA results and supports LCA's role as a decision-support tool for both technology development and policy-relevant reporting.

Future Directions.

The absolute environmental sustainability assessment approach developed within GIGABAT (Ali et al., 2025) represents a promising methodological extension that goes beyond relative benchmarking by anchoring results to science-based planetary boundaries. Its harmonisation across EU battery R&I projects is identified as a priority area for future work, pending wider adoption and methodological consensus.

5. Conclusions

This paper reviewed current practices in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Table 5

Summary of recommendations to enhance consistency and comparability in EU battery LCA studies.

Barrier addressed	Aspect	Minimum Requirement	Recommendation (when feasible / data available)	Rationale
–	System description	Cell mass (kg) Cell energy density (kWh/kg) Pack mass (kg) if relevant Pack energy density (kWh/kg) if relevant Manufacturing energy amount Human-readable inventory Scale (TRL)	Cycle life (if relevant) The inventory should be human-readable and machine-readable	Transparency and reproducibility; FAIR principles
Lack of single guidance document	FU(s)	Report results per 1 kWh of beginning-of-life (BOL) battery capacity; clearly state whether nameplate, usable, or BOL capacity is used Results are provided at least for the cradle-to-gate	Additionally, report results per kWh delivered over lifetime (scenario-based), and document assumptions	Regulatory alignment with DA-EV, CFB-EV, CFB-IND and PEFCR
Lack of single guidance document	System boundaries	Explicitly justify boundary choice; clearly state included/excluded stages If the use stage is included, its modelling should be reported	Include scenario-based modelling of the use phase and EoL where relevant	Consistency with the EU Battery Regulation scope and emerging regulatory practice
End-of-life modelling	Allocation method	Clearly state the allocation method applied (e.g., cut-off, system expansion, CFF); ensure consistency between the allocation choice and the background database system model used.	Apply price-difference allocation for recovered materials where relevant and implement the circular footprint formula	Consistency with cut-off background databases; CFF required by draft delegated act
Lack of primary data / Background data discrepancy	Software and databases	Clearly state the database name, version and system model	Improve representativeness of material inventories (supply routes)	Transparency and reproducibility; FAIR principles
Lack of single guidance document	Impact Assessment Method	Apply the latest available version of the EF method as the default LCIA method; if an alternative method is used, provide an explicit justification	Use ReCiPe only for secondary assessment/continuity with previous literature	Regulatory alignment with the EU Battery Regulation, draft delegated act, and PEFCR
Lack of single guidance document	Environmental impact categories	Clearly state categories assessed and justify any reductions: (i) study scope, (ii) data limitations, or (iii) relevance screening following PEFCR guidance	Apply the latest version of EF midpoint indicators as the default set (PEF-aligned)	PEFCR alignment prevents burden-shifting by covering all impact dimensions
Electricity modelling	Electricity mix(es)	State whether a location-based or market-based approach is used; specify the geographic scope and the electricity mix dataset applied for each production location modelled. Include at least a one-at-a-time local sensitivity analysis covering the electricity mix; clearly report which parameters were varied and the range of results obtained	Include alternative mixes and sourcing in the sensitivity analysis	Consistent with draft delegated act location-based approach
Lack of single guidance document	Sensitivity analysis	State the production scale modelled (e.g., lab, pilot, industrial); if upscaling was applied, document the method used and the key assumptions made. Identify the benchmark study used, justify its selection in relation to the chemistry and scope of the assessed system, and clearly state any differences in methodology between the assessed study and the benchmark	Develop project-level upscaling guidance to reduce variability	Ensures results are relevant for industrial benchmark
Lack of upscaling approaches	Production scale for LCA model		Consider harmonising benchmark choices across projects where feasible	Improves cross-project comparability and contextualisation of results

across five Horizon Europe battery projects—GIGAGREEN, BatWoMan, NoVOC, GIGABAT, and BATMACHINE—to assess methodological alignment and identify sources of variability that affect the comparability of results. The collaboration within the Battery Heroes Sustainability working group proved instrumental in surfacing methodological challenges that are rarely documented in the published literature, and provides a replicable model for cross-project harmonisation in EU-funded research.

The analysis reveals that meaningful convergence is already underway: the shared adoption of 1 kWh of capacity as the FU, ecoinvent as the background database, and EF 3.1 as the impact method assessment reflects a collective move towards regulatory alignment with the EU Battery Regulation and the EF/PEF framework. However, persistent heterogeneity in system boundaries, end-of-life modelling, electricity assumptions, and impact category selection continues to undermine cross-project comparability and limit the policy relevance of LCA outputs. These findings underscore that harmonisation is not merely a methodological preference but a practical necessity for LCA to function as a credible benchmarking tool in the EU Battery R&I.

Data availability and transparency remain structural barriers, particularly at low TRLs. The rapid evolution of background datasets – illustrated by the near-tenfold increase in synthetic graphite GWP between ecoinvent databases – highlights that comparability depends not

only on methodological choices but also on consistent and transparent reporting of database versions and material inventories.

The minimum harmonised reporting set proposed in Table 5 offers a practical pathway to address these challenges without constraining research flexibility. Its adoption across EU-funded battery projects would enhance the credibility and policy relevance of LCA results, support cross-project learning, and facilitate progressive alignment with EF/PEF-based reporting requirements under the EU Battery Regulation.

This study makes several distinct contributions to the existing literature. First, unlike previous reviews that survey the broader battery LCA literature, this work is grounded in active cross-project collaboration among practitioners within five running Horizon Europe projects, providing an evidence-based, insider perspective on methodological challenges that are rarely documented in published studies. Second, while existing guidelines such as the PEFCR, CFB-EV, and CFB-IND address regulatory compliance for commercial batteries, none of these guidelines specifically target the methodological needs of pre-commercial R&I projects at low TRLs – a gap this paper directly addresses. Third, the proposed minimum harmonised reporting set goes beyond descriptive comparison by offering concrete, actionable recommendations that bridge the gap between research practice and emerging EU regulatory requirements, including the EU Battery Regulation and the EF/PEF framework. Finally, by documenting the

evolution of background database values and their implications for comparability, this paper highlights a largely overlooked source of inconsistency with direct practical relevance for the field.

This review is limited to a subset of Horizon Europe battery projects selected based on the availability of documentation and active cross-project collaboration. As of 2024, the Horizon Europe programme has funded 79 battery-related projects covering the entire value chain (Zabala, 2025). The five projects reviewed here were selected based on their membership in the Battery Heroes cluster, which was established to facilitate voluntary cross-project collaboration on LCA and sustainability. While the projects cover a range of chemistries, technology objectives and maturity levels, the sample is not exhaustive and may not fully represent the diversity of LCA practices across all EU-funded battery initiatives. In addition, several projects are ongoing, and their full LCA/LCSA studies are still under development, meaning that some methodological choices may evolve as more primary data becomes available and as regulatory guidance is finalised.

Overall, strengthening methodological alignment and transparency across EU-funded battery projects will enhance credibility and policy relevance of LCA results, support cross-project learning, and facilitate progressive alignment with EF/PEF-based reporting requirements under the EU Battery Regulation. Future work should prioritise: the development of standardised upscaling approaches for pre-commercial technologies; improved access to high-quality primary data; harmonisation of social LCA practices within LCSA frameworks; and considering the broader adoption of absolute environmental sustainability assessment approaches to complement relative benchmarking. Continued collaborative platforms – such as cross-project working groups – will be essential to sustain this momentum and support the transition towards more sustainable and circular battery value chains in Europe.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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